

ANALYSIS AND APPROXIMATION OF FLUTTER STABILITY FOR SYNTHETIC MODE SHAPES

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ABSTRACT

Stall flutter limits fan operating range and constrains design flexibility. While extensive research has explored its mechanisms, stability criteria remain unclear, including the influence of mode shape composition and frequency. Lower reduced frequencies and increased torsional content are known to promote instability, but critical thresholds vary across designs. Mapping stability against these parameters typically requires numerous resource-intensive aeroelastic simulations.

This paper introduces and validates an efficient approach based on decomposing mode shapes into fundamental bending and torsional components derived from beam theory. Synthetic modes with arbitrary torsional content are constructed by superposing these components, and their stability is predicted using aeroelastic results from the two fundamental modes. This formalized method, applied for the first time to a transonic fan across a wide frequency range, demonstrates significant computational savings while improving physical interpretability. Results confirm the influence of acoustic effects on flutter stability and reveal a linear relationship between aerodynamic work input and frequency in cut-on regions. The study further shows that complex flutter trends can be decomposed into simpler contributions, enabling the development of a novel reduced-order model for stability prediction.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Transonic Flutter, Stability Map, Reduced Order Model

NOMENCLATURE

c tip chord length
 d weight of fundamental modes
 f vibration frequency
 f_{down} cut-on frequency downstream of the blade

f_{norm} frequency normalised by cut-on frequency
 f_{up} cut-on frequency upstream of the blade
 k reduced frequency $\frac{wC}{v_c}$
 $l=c$ non-dimensional torsion axis location
 Ma_x inlet Mach number
 m_m modal mass
 \mathbf{M} mass matrix
 N number of blades
 ND nodal diameter
 \mathbf{n} normal vector
 ρ static pressure
 P_0 stagnation pressure
 S surface of blade
 T period of vibration
 T_0 stagnation temperature
 v_c characteristic velocity
 \mathbf{v} blade velocity vector
 W work input
 \hat{q} modal displacement amplitude
 f plunge-to-twist incidence ratio
 F mode shape vector
 w angular vibration frequency
 z critical damping ratio

subscripts

B bending
 C combined
 LE leading edge
 T torsion
 TE trailing edge

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of modern jet engines is driven by the need to reduce fuel consumption, leading to higher bypass ratios and the use of low-pressure ratio fan blades, also often referred to as low-speed fans. Similarly to previous generations of fan blades, these blades are prone to stall flutter. This aeroelastic instability occurs near the stall boundary and limits the operability of the jet engine in the part-speed region.

Over the past decades, fan blade flutter has been studied extensively [1–3] due to its safety critical nature. Thereby, several influencing factors have been identified: the operating point [4], the impact of reduced frequency and fundamental mode shape contributions [5–8] as well as the acoustic condition [9, 10].

The effect of reduced frequency and fundamental mode shape contributions on flutter stability is known since the early days of flutter research on flat plates and two-dimensional cascades [11, 12]. Fundamental mode shape contributions refer to the relative components of torsion and bending in a mode shape. It has been identified that low reduced frequency and increased torsional components increase the risk for flutter. This has been confirmed for current fan, compressor, and turbine geometries in more recent research [6, 8, 9, 13].

Fan stability maps, which plot aerodynamic damping as a function of reduced frequency $k = \frac{wC}{V_c}$ and non-dimensional torsion axis location $l=c$, are commonly used to assess flutter risk. The relevance of these parameters has been established in classical studies such as [5], and further explored for modern fan configurations by [8, 13]. However, generating these maps typically requires extensive simulations across a two-dimensional design space, making the process computationally demanding.

A theoretical approach to assess the flutter stability based on the synthesis of aerodynamic work for two-dimensional cascades has been derived in [7] and applied to multiple configurations in [14]. This approach allows the estimation of aerodynamic damping based on the aerodynamic work input as a function of reduced frequency. However, the study is limited to two-dimensional cascades so far and does not account for the complex three-dimensional nature of modern fan blades.

The main objectives of this paper are to

1. Formalise and validate an efficient methodology for determining aerodynamic damping for arbitrary mode shapes based on aerodynamic damping in fundamental modes.
2. Show that the complex aerodynamic damping dependency on mode shape and reduced frequency seen in literature can be broken down sufficiently to identify simpler trends, laying the ground work for physical explanations of flutter.
3. Demonstrate the feasibility of developing empirical (surrogated) or physics-based (reduced order) models for fast flutter prediction based on the trends identified in (2).

The paper is structured into four main parts. Firstly, the test case and computational setup are described in Sec. 2. Secondly,

the theory behind the synthesis of mode shape and aerodynamic work input is presented in Sec. 3 and the proposed superposition approach is validated. Thirdly, the stability map of the test case is presented in Sec. 4, and the contributions of the different mode shape components to the overall stability are discussed. Finally, a simple reduced order model is proposed to demonstrate the practical applicability of the findings.

2 TEST CASE AND COMPUTATIONAL SETUP

The computational analysis is performed on a transonic fan rig geometry representative of modern low-pressure ratio systems [15]. During experimental testing the fan fluttered in the first flap, second nodal diameter (1F, ND2) mode in a narrow speed range in the part-speed region. Key design parameters are summarised in Table 1.

In a previous publication, a computational model of the entire rig (intake, fan and outlet guide vane) was validated and analysed. The fan operating map is reproduced in Fig. 1 for reference. In addition, the experimental flutter boundary is shown in red and the investigated operating point, i.e. point with zero aerodynamic damping during the rig test, is highlighted in red. The flutter point is captured well in the simulations. The interested reader is referred to [15] for a more detailed validation and analysis.

TABLE 1: FAN DESIGN PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Hub-to-tip ratio	0.256
Inlet Mach number Ma_x	0.38
Blade number N	18
Reduced frequency $k = \frac{wC}{V_c}$	0.45
Non-dimensional torsion axis location $l=c$	1.45

2.1 Flow solver

All computations presented in this report were obtained using the unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) in-house solver AU3D. The solution method is implicit and second-order accurate in space and time. Further details of the flow solver are provided by [16]. AU3D has been developed at Imperial College with the support of Rolls-Royce and has been extensively validated for fan flutter analysis [2, 9, 15, 17]. All simulations in this paper use a modified Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model with a pressure gradient and helicity correction. Details

FIGURE 1: COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL FAN PERFORMANCE FOR THE WHOLE LOW-PRESSURE SYSTEM, ADAPTED FROM [15]

FIGURE 2: COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN USED FOR UNSTEADY AERODYNAMIC AIC SIMULATIONS

and validation of the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model for low-pressure ratio fans are given by [17].

2.2 Computational model and approach

The present study aims to explore the influence of mode shape on flutter sensitivity and hence uses a modified computational domain, shown in Fig. 2, comprised only of the fan, an extended duct upstream and downstream of the fan, and a choked nozzle. Total pressure, total temperature and flow angles are prescribed at the inlet boundary and the mass flow at the outlet is controlled by the size of the choked nozzle. The ducts upstream and downstream of the fan are extended to 24 fan diameters and 73 fan diameters respectively. The mesh is coarsening away from the fan to remove any acoustic reflections, which would influence aerodynamic damping. The absence of numerical reflections was verified by tracking pressures in the ducts and the transients of aerodynamic damping on the fan blade.

The grid is structured radially and unstructured in the cir-

FIGURE 3: REFERENCE DAMPING CURVE FOR 1F MODE AT URANS OPERATING POINT SHOWN AS RED POINT IN FIG. 1

cumferential direction. The fan mesh is the same employed in [15], where it was validated for flutter predictions. There are 50 mesh layers in the radial direction, refined towards the tip. The tip clearance is resolved with 10 layers. Throughout this study, wall functions are used, and the grid size is set to $y^+ = 30$. The final single passage mesh of the fan contains approximately 250,000 points.

The aerodynamic damping analysis is performed on a full annulus domain using URANS and the Aerodynamic Influence Coefficient (AIC) method, where one blade is vibrating in harmonic motion and the resulting unsteady forces on all other blades are used to calculate aerodynamic damping for all travelling wave modes (nodal diameters). A full explanation of the AIC method is given in [18]. For brevity, unsteady aerodynamic damping simulations will be referred to as AIC simulations in the rest of the paper.

2.3 Choice of operating condition

All results presented in this paper are for a constant operating point very close to the stability boundary, indicated in 1 by a red dot. The critical damping ratio for the first flap (1F) mode at this condition is $z = 0.004\%$, i.e. the fan is stable but very close to zero. It will be seen later that it becomes unstable when the twist content of the mode shape is increased. The damping curve of all nodal diameters is shown in Fig. 3. The least stable nodal diameters are ND0, ND1 and ND2. Since ND0 is rarely unstable in real applications, the analysis of the following sections will focus on ND1 and ND2.

3 SYNTHESIS OF MODE SHAPES AND AERODYNAMIC WORK INPUT

To study the influence of reduced frequency and bending-torsion composition on flutter stability, the fan mode shape is parametrised and varied systematically. This section describes the methodology used to construct synthetic mode shapes based on fundamental modes and determine the aerodynamic work input for a given mode shape based on superposition of the work input of the associated fundamental modes. Aerodynamic work input, instead of aerodynamic damping, is used as a measure of stability as it allows the characterisation of the unsteady aerodynamic response independent of modal mass.

This section describes the decomposition of real mode shapes and subsequent construction of artificial mode shapes first; it then introduces the non-dimensional torsion axis location, $l=c$, as the key parameter. The superposition of work input for a given non-dimensional torsion axis location is then explained. Finally, the superposition approach is validated against AIC simulations with modified mode shapes to produce non-dimensional torsion axis locations in the industry relevant range of $l=c = 0.5$ to 4.0 .

3.1 Modal decomposition and construction of synthetic modes

The modal decomposition approach is based on the idea that the actual mode shape of a complex three-dimensional aerofoil can be represented as a superposition of fundamental modes. These fundamental modes are typically represented by bending, torsion, tramline and higher mode orders. This can be expressed mathematically as

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i F_i \quad (1)$$

where F is the original mode shape of the aerofoil, and d_i are the weights for each fundamental mode F_i . An example of each of the first three fundamental mode shapes is shown at the top of Fig. 4. Based on these fundamental modes, the original mode shape can be reconstructed with the original weights, new synthetic mode shapes can be tailored by varying the weights d_i for sensitivity studies, or the work input of fundamental modes can be used to reconstruct aerodynamic work input based on a superposition approach as proposed in this research.

Beam analogies with different boundary conditions in chordwise and radial direction can be used to derive the fundamental contributions of a complex three-dimensional mode shape. The fundamental beam modes can be determined by iteratively solving the eigenvalue problem of the beam equation. At each radial location, the mode shape is decomposed into bending, torsion, tramline and higher modes. The resulting mode shapes

FIGURE 4: MODE DECOMPOSITION MATRIX SHOWING THE RELATIVE CONTRIBUTION OF FUNDAMENTAL MODES TO THE 1F MODE. FIRST THREE FUNDAMENTAL MODE SHAPES SHOWN AT THE TOP AND RADIAL MODE SHAPE DECOMPOSITION VISUALIZED FOR BENDING MODE.

are shown at the top of Fig. 4. Each of these fundamental modes can be decomposed in radial direction into radial mode orders in a next step. This is visualized in Fig. 4 for the first three radial mode orders of the bending mode. Hereby, the radial order can be identified as the number of nodal lines present in radial direction.

Their relative contribution with respect to the original mode can be determined with a least-square fitting and results in a $n \times m$ decomposition matrix as shown in Fig. 4. For the shown example, n and m have been chosen to be 3, as higher contributions are negligible ($< 1\%$). From the decomposition matrix in Fig. 4, it can be seen that the bending and torsion modes at zeroth radial order have the largest contribution to the original mode shape with a weight factor of 0.63 and 0.33. These two modes will be referred to as pure bending (B) and pure torsion (T) throughout the rest of the paper. Higher mode orders are neglected in the presented study.

The resulting combined mode (C) can be constructed as a linear combination of the pure bending and pure torsion modes according to

$$F_C = d_B F_B + d_T F_T \quad (2)$$

and is visualized in Fig. 5. The mode shapes F_B and F_T have been scaled by the original mode shape in a way that weights

(a) pure bending mode (b) pure torsion mode (c) combined mode

FIGURE 5: RECONSTRUCTION OF A COMBINED MODE (c) BASED ON THE PURE BENDING MODE (a) AND PURE TORSION MODE (b) - MODES CONTAINING ONLY THE 0TH RADIAL ORDER.

of $d_B = d_T = 1$ results in the original mode shape minus higher mode orders.

3.2 Non-dimensional torsion axis location, $l=c$

Fig. 6 shows a sketch of an aerofoil cross-section displaced in a pure plunging and twisting motion created by bending or torsion of the blade to visualize the definition of the non-dimensional torsion axis location. The mode shape vector of the combined mode shape F is visualized as arrow at the leading edge (LE) and trailing edge (TE), respectively. The non-dimensional torsion axis location, referred to as $l=c$, is the ratio of the distance from the leading edge to the torsion axis location l and the chord length of the aerofoil, c . The torsion axis location is defined as the point about which the aerofoil twists, and it is influenced by the fundamental mode shapes and their contributions to the overall deformation. Several studies have shown that the non-dimensional torsion axis location, $l=c$, is a key parameter in the analysis of fan flutter stability [5, 6, 8, 17].

FIGURE 6: DEFINITION OF NON-DIMENSIONAL TORSION AXIS LOCATION AT THE TIP OF THE BLADE WITH UNDEFORMED (LINED) AND DEFORMED (DASHED) BLADE GEOMETRY, ADAPTED FROM [13].

With the assumption of small perturbations and the consideration of pure bending and pure torsion modes only, the non-dimensional torsion axis location can be expressed in terms of the newly defined synthetic modes (Eq. 2)

$$\frac{l}{c} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d_B jF_{B:LEj}}{d_T jF_{T:LEj}} + 1 \quad (3)$$

where $jF_{B:LEj}$ and $jF_{T:LEj}$ are the magnitudes of the bending and torsion mode shapes at the leading edge and d_B and d_T are the weights of the pure bending and torsion modes respectively. To satisfy the assumption of small displacements, the weights d_B and d_T are constrained to keep the magnitude of the physical displacement at the leading edge tip constant at 0.3% chord, i.e. $jF_{LEj} = d_B jF_{B:LEj} + d_T jF_{T:LEj} = \text{constant}$.

Several studies [8, 19] have identified the plunge-to-twist incidence ratio f as an important design parameter for fan flutter stability. The plunge-to-twist incidence ratio reads

$$f = k \frac{l}{c} \frac{1}{2} \quad (4)$$

as a function of reduced frequency k and non-dimensional torsion axis location $l=c$. It describes the relationship between the incidence induced by the torsion motion and the effective change in incidence induced by the bending velocity. The generality of the plunge-to-twist incidence ratio f for fan flutter stability will be discussed in Sec. 4.

3.3 Superposition of aerodynamic work input

The purpose of the mode decomposition and reconstruction is that the aerodynamic work input for any synthetic mode defined by Eq. 2 can be calculated from only two simulations, one for pure bending and one for pure torsion, by superposing the aerodynamic work contributions. The work done by the fluid on the blade can be expressed as a linear combination of the work done by the fundamental modes. Hereby, the velocity, v_C , and pressure, p_C of the combined mode shape are assumed to be a linear combination of their fundamental counterparts

$$\begin{aligned} v_C &= d_B v_B + d_T v_T \\ p_C &= d_B p_B + d_T p_T \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where subscripts B and T denote the bending and torsion modes respectively, and d_B and d_T are the weights for the bending and torsion modes. This assumption holds true for small perturbations. In [9] it was shown that the total work $W_{CC} = W_{BB} + W_{BT} + W_{TT} + W_{TB}$ for d_B and d_T equal to 1. An overview about these work contributions is given in Table 2. The approach can be ex-

TABLE 2: DEFINITION OF FUNDAMENTAL MODE CONTRIBUTIONS TO AERODYNAMIC WORK INPUT

W_{BB}	Work by bending-induced force in the bending motion
W_{TB}	Work by torsion-induced force in the bending motion
W_{BT}	Work by bending-induced force in the torsion motion
W_{TT}	Work by torsion-induced force in the torsion motion

tended to arbitrary values of d_B and d_T without loss of generality. Therefore, the total work done by the fluid on the blade over one vibration cycle W_{CC} can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_{CC} &= \int_{Z^S}^Z \rho c \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_C dS dt \\
 &= d_B^2 \int_{Z^S}^Z \frac{\rho_B \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_B dS dt}{W_{BB}} + d_B d_T \int_{Z^S}^Z \frac{\rho_B \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_T dS dt}{W_{BT}} \\
 &\quad + d_T^2 \int_{Z^S}^Z \frac{\rho_T \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_T dS dt}{W_{TT}} + d_T d_B \int_{Z^S}^Z \frac{\rho_T \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{v}_B dS dt}{W_{TB}}
 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where each work contribution corresponds to the definitions given in Table 2. Eq. 6 allows the calculation of the total work input for any synthetic mode constructed by Eq. 2. This superposition will be used to efficiently generate fan flutter stability maps in Sec. 4, showing the aerodynamic work input as a function of reduced frequency and non-dimensional torsion axis location.

For small values of aerodynamic damping and structures with neglectible mechanical damping, the critical damping ratio z can be represented as

$$z = \frac{W}{2\rho m_m \hat{q}^2 w^2} \quad (7)$$

where W is the aerodynamic work input, $m_m = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{F}$ is the modal mass, \hat{q} is the modal displacement amplitude and w is the angular frequency. From this, it can be seen that the modal mass has a significant influence on aerodynamic damping. For cases where the modal mass of the fundamental mode shapes is known, it can be shown mathematically that the scaling factors are constrained by $1 = d_B^2 + d_T^2$ to keep the modal mass constant. For reasons of brevity, the lengthy derivation is not shown here. This is not satisfied in the present study and instead of damping, trends in work input will be analysed.

3.4 Validation of superposition method

The superposition of aerodynamic work input (Eq. 6) is now validated for a range of torsion axis locations by comparing it

FIGURE 7: VALIDATION OF MODAL RECONSTRUCTION METHOD FOR TWO REDUCED FREQUENCIES IN ND1

against aerodynamic work input calculated from selected unsteady aerodynamic damping simulations (AIC) with synthetic mode shapes. The work input of both approaches is shown in Fig. 7 for two reduced frequencies $k = \frac{wC}{v_c}$ in ND1. The AIC results are shown as black crosses, while the superposition is shown as dashed lines. Mode shapes with non-dimensional torsion axis locations in the red area are unstable.

The results show a good agreement between the two approaches, with the superposition method being able to accurately predict the work input for the different non-dimensional torsion axis locations. With this, it is possible to reduce the required aeroelastic simulations to two only per reduced frequency, a simulation with a pure bending mode shape and a simulation with a pure torsion mode shape. The synthesis of mode shape and aerodynamic work input is not limited to the here used unsteady aerodynamic AIC simulations, but can be used in combination with any aeroelastic method that provides work input or damping values.

4 ANALYSIS OF FAN STABILITY

The superposition method described in Sec. 3 is now used to calculate the aerodynamic work input for a range of reduced frequencies and non-dimensional torsion axis locations to create a stability map as seen in other studies [8, 13, 19]. The total aerodynamic work input will be decomposed into its fundamental contributions, which will be analysed in detail to describe trends and can be used to develop an approximation method.

FIGURE 8: STABILITY MAP FOR ND1. POSITIVE WORK INPUT IS DESTABILISING. THE DASHED BLACK AND RED LINES INDICATE THE CUT-ON BOUNDARY FOR UPSTREAM AND DOWNSTREAM PROPAGATING ACOUSTIC WAVES RESPECTIVELY. PURPLE AND GREEN LINES INDICATE CONSTANT PLUNGE-TO-TWIST INCIDENCE RATIO f (EQ. 4) OF 0.4 AND 1.0 RESPECTIVELY.

4.1 Stability map for ND1

The stability map of the transonic fan test case for ND1 is shown in Fig. 8. Work input was reconstructed for a range from $l=c = 0.5$ to $l=c = 4.0$ in steps of 0.01. This was achieved from two simulations, pure bending and pure torsion as previously explained. To populate the data in the y-axis, however, two simulations at 20 discrete reduced frequencies have been performed to obtain the necessary data points. The interpolated colormap represents the aerodynamic work input, where areas with positive work input are shown in red and indicate a destabilising effect on the blade. The black line indicates the stability limit, which is defined by the combination of k and $l=c$ where the work input is zero. The plot also shows two lines (0.4 and 1.0) of constant plunge-to-twist incidence ratio f , as defined by Eq. 4. In this test case, however, it is clear that the stability boundary does not lie along a line of constant incidence ratio.

In line with previous findings [13], the stability map shows a clear trend of increasing stability with either increasing k or increasing $l=c$. Due to the wide range of frequencies included here, two separate destabilising regions can be identified for $l=c$ values below 2.0. One is located at k values between 0.26 and 0.65, the other one at k values below 0.26.

To further investigate the source for these regions, the corresponding cut on frequencies upstream (black) and downstream (red) of the blade are shown as dashed lines. It is clearly visible, that the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade, which is located at $k = 0.26$, is the separating factor of both regions. In addition,

FIGURE 9: OVERALL, PRESSURE AND SUCTION SIDE CONTRIBUTIONS TO AERODYNAMIC WORK INPUT AT NON-DIMENSIONAL TORSION AXIS LOCATION $l=c = 1.45$ AS FUNCTION OF FREQUENCY NORMALISED BY CUT-ON FREQUENCIES (EQ. 8)

the stability map shows a trend change at $k = 0.31$, which is the cut-on frequency downstream of the blade. For the test case investigated here, $k = 0.31$ is also the reduced frequency where the stability boundary reaches the highest $l=c$ value. The importance of the acoustic conditions is already shown in other studies [3,9]. However, compared to [9], the blade is unstable outside the ‘cut-on upstream, cut-off downstream’ condition and the negative region extends below the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade. A similar behaviour is also reported in [3]. It has to be noted that the acoustic condition is not just defining that a travelling wave is cut-on in axial direction, but waves in circumferential direction at this frequency can propagate without attenuation as well. For example, in [10] the focus was on the axial direction and the intake effect on flutter, while the present study highlights the importance of the circumferential direction as reflections upstream and downstream of the blade are avoided.

In the next step, the aerodynamic work input will be split into contributions from the pressure side and suction side. An example is shown in Fig. 9 for a constant non-dimensional torsion axis location of $l=c = 1.45$, which is the synthetic mode closest to the original 1F mode. The red line, which represents the sum of the suction and pressure side contributions, is data along a vertical line of the stability map and therefore shows the same trends as the stability map in Fig. 8, with a sharp drop in aerodynamic work input near the upstream cut-on frequency (dashed grey line), as well as the gradual decrease in work input above the downstream cut-on frequency (red dashed line). The decomposition into pressure side (green) and suction side (blue) shows that the pressure side is mainly responsible for positive

FIGURE 10: FUNDAMENTAL WORK CONTRIBUTIONS FOR ND1 AS FUNCTIONS OF FREQUENCY NORMALISED BY CUT-ON FREQUENCIES (EQ. 8), BLACK CIRCLES SHOW NORMALISED FREQUENCIES WHERE LOCAL WORK IS ANALYSED.

work input in regions below the downstream cut-on frequency, while it is mainly the suction side that is responsible for positive work input in the region where the frequency is cut-on upstream and downstream. The following sections will further investigate these findings for the fundamental mode shape contributions to allow a better understanding of the underlying physical mechanisms.

4.2 Reduction of stability map into mode shape contributions

The stability of a blade can be considered as a superposition of work input of fundamental mode shapes, as it has been described in the previous Sec. 3. The aerodynamic work input in the fundamental mode shapes depends only on reduced frequency, k , and hence it is possible to reduce the two-dimensional representation of the stability map into a one-dimensional representation of the fundamental mode shape contributions. These contributions are given by Eq. 6, they are summarised in Table 2, and further referred to as W_{BB} , W_{TB} , W_{BT} and W_{TT} .

These work input contributions are shown in Fig. 10 for a range of reduced frequencies k of 0.05 to 0.9 and split into their suction side and pressure side part. To emphasise the influence of the acoustic conditions, the reduced frequencies are normalised by the cut-on frequencies according to

$$f_{norm} = \begin{cases} \geq f = f_{up}; & f < f_{up} \\ 1 + \frac{f - f_{up}}{f_{down} - f_{up}}; & f_{up} < f < f_{down} \\ \geq \frac{f - f_{down}}{f_{down} - f_{down}}; & f > f_{down} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where f_{up} and f_{down} are the cut-on frequencies upstream and downstream of the blade, respectively. The mapping was chosen in a way that the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade is equal to 1 and the cut-on frequency downstream of the blade is equal to 2.

In an effort to further investigate the trends in Fig. 10, it is important to note the differences in magnitudes of the work contributions. While the bending-induced work in the bending motion W_{BB} and the torsion-induced work in the bending motion W_{TB} are of similar magnitude, W_{BT} and W_{TT} are significantly smaller. Therefore, the analysis will mainly focus on W_{BB} and W_{TB} .

Comparing the green and blue lines in Fig. 9 to the lines in Fig. 10, it is clear to see that the contribution of W_{BB} sets the shape of the overall work input on suction side and pressure side, while the contribution of W_{TB} adds an additional offset to the overall work input. This offset determines if the blade is stable or unstable, especially in the region where the upstream acoustic wave is cut-on, but the downstream acoustic wave is cut-off. For the work input W_{BB} , the pressure side is destabilising the blade near the upstream cut-on frequency, while it is the suction side that destabilises the blade near the downstream cut-on frequency. Both, the pressure side and suction side, are stabilising (negative work input) the blade for frequencies where both acoustic conditions are cut-on. The work input W_{TB} on the pressure side is always destabilising, while the work input W_{TB} on the suction side is only destabilising in the region where the frequency is cut-on upstream and downstream.

4.3 Distribution of work input over blade surface

The local work contributions on the blade surface for the non-dimensional torsion axis location $l=c = 1.45$ will be analysed in more detail to explain some of the observed trends for different acoustic regions. Therefore, three different reduced frequencies k between 0.24 and 0.36 are selected, which represent one of the three acoustic regions with a focus on the previously identified major work input contributions of bending-induced force in the bending motion W_{BB} and torsion-induced force in the bending motion W_{TB} . The corresponding normalised frequencies are marked by black circles in Fig. 10 for reference.

Influence of bending-induced local work

The local work on the blade surface is shown in Fig. 11 for W_{BB} at different acoustic conditions. The blade surface is normalised by its chordwise and spanwise position to allow a more unified comparison between suction side and pressure side. Areas of positive work input (destabilising) are shown in red, while areas of negative work input (stabilising) are shown in blue. The limit of zero work input is shown as black line.

FIGURE 11: LOCAL WORK INPUT FOR ND1 OF BENDING-INDUCED WORK ON THE BENDING MOTION W_{BB} AT DIFFERENT REDUCED FREQUENCIES

In Fig. 11a, it can be seen that the suction side has a major stable contribution due to the shock, while the pressure side is mainly unstable with small stable regions near the leading edge

and trailing edge close to the tip. This aligns well with the previously identified trends in Fig. 10.

In Fig. 11b, the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade is reached, which leads to a change in the stability on both, suction side and pressure side. While the shock remains stable, the after shock region on the suction side becomes more unstable with increasing frequency. In contrast, the pressure side becomes fully stabilising once the upstream travelling ND1 pressure wave becomes cut-on. At this condition, the pressure wave can propagate around the circumference close to the leading edge. These trends can then also be seen in Fig. 11c, where the pressure waves upstream and downstream of the blade can propagate in circumferential and axial directions. In addition, the leading edge region on the suction side becomes more stabilising with higher frequencies, which explains the trend change on the suction side in Fig. 10.

Influence of torsion-induced local work

The local work on the blade surface is shown in Fig. 12 for W_{TB} , in the same way as for W_{BB} before. By comparing the pressure side for all three acoustic conditions, it can be seen that the pressure side is mainly unstable and only subtle changes occur as the frequency is increased beyond the cut-on frequency downstream. These subtle changes are mainly constrained to the leading edge region and affect frequencies that are greater than the cut-on frequencies on both sides of the blade.

For the suction side, it can be seen that the shock region is stable for low frequencies, but parts of it become unstable as soon as the pressure wave downstream of the blade can propagate in circumferential direction. This shock behaviour, which switches from negative work input to positive work input, can be identified as one of the causes for the major drop in stability in Fig. 10. Additionally, the region below the shock foot near the hub becomes unstable as well. Other regions of the suction side are not changing significantly with frequency. For example, the after shock region at the tip of the blade remains unstable for the whole frequency range and the trailing edge region is stabilising for a wide frequency range.

4.4 Influence of nodal diameter and resulting scalability of trends

While the previous sections focused on a single nodal diameter (ND1), it is of interest to analyse the influence of nodal diameters on the described stability trends. By moving from ND1 to higher nodal diameters, the acoustic conditions and, therefore, the frequency range changes. To account for this, the previously mentioned mapping of frequencies according to Eq. 8 is now applied to each nodal diameter separately. As a result, all cut-on frequencies upstream of the blade are aligned at 1 and all cut-off frequencies downstream of the blade are aligned at 2.

In Fig. 13, the total work for a non-dimensional torsion axis location of $l=c = 1.45$ is shown for different nodal diameters.

FIGURE 12: LOCAL WORK INPUT FOR ND1 OF TORSION-INDUCED WORK ON THE BENDING MOTION W_{TB} AT DIFFERENT REDUCED FREQUENCIES

Each line style represents a different nodal diameter, with ND1 being the solid lines, ND2 the dashed lines, ND3 the dotted lines.

It can be seen that the overall work input dependency on frequency shows similarities for all nodal diameters. Positive work input is observed for low frequencies across all nodal diameters and becomes negative close to the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade. But for higher nodal diameters, all frequencies greater than the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade remain negative, while for ND1, the frequencies close to the cut-on frequency downstream of the blade show positive work input.

By comparing the pressure side and suction side contributions, it can be seen that the suction side is mainly responsible for the negative work input in the low frequency range, while the

FIGURE 13: PRESSURE AND SUCTION SIDE CONTRIBUTIONS TO AERODYNAMIC WORK INPUT FOR DIFFERENT NODAL DIAMETERS AGAINST NORMALISED FREQUENCY AT NON-DIMENSIONAL TORSION AXIS LOCATION $l=c = 1.45$

pressure side is mainly responsible for the negative work input in the high frequency range. Hereby, the pressure side shows more negative work input with higher nodal diameters for higher frequencies. This can be identified as one of the main causes for the trend of higher nodal diameters showing no positive work close to the region where the frequency downstream of the blade is cut-on. Hence, even though the trends are similar for all nodal diameters, ND2 and ND3 show no unstable region when the frequency is cut-on upstream of the blade.

While the overall work input indicated similar trends for all nodal diameters, the individual contributions to the aerodynamic work input allow a more detailed understanding. The two largest fundamental work input contributions (W_{BB} and W_{TB}) to the total work input are shown in Fig. 14 for different reduced frequencies k and split into their suction side and pressure side part.

Similar to the trends shown in the analysis of Fig. 10, W_{BB} defines the overall shape of the work input, while W_{TB} adds an additional offset to the overall work input and defines if the blade is stable or unstable. The pressure side of W_{BB} introduces positive work input for frequencies below the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade, while becomes negative for higher frequencies and with increasing magnitude for higher nodal diameter. On the suction side, W_{BB} shows large negative work input close the cut-on frequency upstream of the blade, introduced positive work close to the cut-on frequency downstream of the blade and becomes negative again for higher frequencies. The pressure side of W_{TB} shows a similar trend for all nodal diameters, and always contributes positive work input, especially pronounced in the region where the upstream frequency is cut-on and the downstream fre-

FIGURE 14: FUNDAMENTAL WORK INPUT CONTRIBUTIONS FOR DIFFERENT NODAL DIAMETERS AS FUNCTION OF NORMALISED FREQUENCY AT NON-DIMENSIONAL TORSION AXIS LOCATION $l=c = 1.45$

quency is cut-off. The magnitude of in this region increases with higher nodal diameter. A same trend can be seen on the suction side for this frequency range, but with negative work input. Below and above these frequencies, both sides have a very similar positive work input contribution for all nodal diameters.

In summary, similarities in trends for the stability map and the fundamental contributions to the aerodynamic work input can be observed for all nodal diameters, but with varying magnitudes. These findings suggest that while the overall behavior is consistent and the same physical mechanisms produce work input, the specific impacts of nodal diameter on aerodynamic performance should be considered in more detail in future research. It will be important to further investigate the reason for the differences in magnitude between different nodal diameters and their implications for approximation methods. Nevertheless, the shown results suggest that any reduced order model developed for ND1, if proven effective, could also be applied to higher nodal diameters due to their similarities. A reduced order model for ND1 will be presented next.

4.5 Approximation of work input by reduced order model

The previously described trends and newly gained insights can be used to derive a very simple reduced order model based on a linear approximation for the frequency dependency of work input and the superposition of work input for non-dimensional torsion axis locations. The here shown example focuses on the region where the frequency is cut-on in both directions, as it is the most relevant region for the investigated transonic fan blade.

In a first step, the fundamental contributions of work input

W_{BB} , W_{BT} , W_{TT} , and W_{TB} can be approximated as a linear function of reduced frequency k . Hereby, a linear function of the form $f(k) = ak + b$ is used, where a is the gradient and b is the y-intercept. The coefficients are determined by two discrete points of each work input contribution in Fig. 10. For the here shown example, the cut-on frequency downstream of the blade and the highest simulated frequency have been used. With this, the fundamental work contributions for ND1 can be approximated by only 4 AIC simulations, a pure bending and pure torsion simulation at each frequency.

In the next step, these fundamental work contributions can be superimposed according to Eq. 6 with the corresponding weights d_B and d_T to create a stability map for ND1 as a function of reduced frequency k and non-dimensional torsion axis location $l=c$. It is important to include W_{TT} and W_{TB} in the superposition to accurately capture the stability behavior. Even though their contribution is small in regions close to the cut-on frequencies, it becomes more pronounced for higher frequencies, as can be seen in Fig. 10. Additionally, their influence due to the weight factors d_B and d_T needs to be considered, as they can affect the overall stability map for different non-dimensional torsion axis locations.

An example of such an approximation is shown in Figure 15. Hereby, the linear approximation of work input for normalized frequencies is linked to the y-axis in terms of reduced frequency. Values along the x-axis are based on the superposition of aerodynamic work input for different non-dimensional torsion axis locations. The stability limit is shown in black, while the true stability limit (based on 40 AIC simulations) is shown in green. The approximated stability map is based on four AIC simulations for ND1. Even though a linear approximation is a

FIGURE 15: APPROXIMATE STABILITY MAP AND STABILITY LIMIT (BLACK) FOR ND1 BASED ON FOUR AIC SIMULATIONS. THE TRUE STABILITY LIMIT IS SHOWN IN GREEN.

very simple approach, it captures the main trends of the stability map and can be used to quickly assess the stability of the fan for different mode shapes.

The same model can be applied to higher nodal diameters, and with further analysis the model may be further reducible to apply to multiple nodal diameters directly. Similar approximations in other frequency regions are also plausible but out of scope of this paper. The linear approximation is sufficient to show the potential of the modal decomposition approach and the insights gained from the analysis of the fan stability.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This paper describes and validates a superposition methodology to calculate aerodynamic damping for arbitrary mode shapes. These mode shapes are synthesised from pure bending and torsion modes. The methodology is applied in a parametric study to generate a stability map, showing the influence of non-dimensional torsion axis location and reduced frequency on flutter stability. Furthermore, it improves physical interpretability and reveals clear trends in aerodynamic work input:

- A clear dependency on acoustic conditions is visible for the investigated fan, consistent with findings in literature [3]. The most destabilising combination of reduced frequency and torsion axis location occurs near the downstream cut-on frequency. Contrary to previous research [8, 13], the stability limit does not follow a line of constant plunge-to-twist incidence ratio \bar{f} .
- The dominant contributions to aerodynamic work input are

bending-induced work in the bending motion (W_{BB}) and torsion-induced work in the bending motion (W_{TB}).

- W_{BB} defines the frequency-dependent shape of the aerodynamic work input. The pressure side destabilises the blade near the upstream cut-on frequency, while the suction side does so near the downstream cut-on frequency. At higher frequencies, both sides contribute stabilising work input.
- W_{TB} introduces an offset to the overall work input, which determines where the blade is stable or unstable, especially in the cut-on cut-off region. The pressure side is consistently destabilising, whereas the suction side becomes destabilising when both upstream and downstream frequencies are cut-on.
- The aerodynamic work input shows similar frequency-dependent trends for all nodal diameters (ND1–ND3), but the magnitude and stability behavior differ. ND1 exhibits unstable regions near the downstream cut-on frequency, while ND2 and ND3 do not.
- The same trends can be confirmed for ND1 to ND3 when decomposing the work input into its fundamental contributions. W_{BB} defines the overall shape, while W_{TB} adds an offset that determines stability.

Based on these newly gained insights, a simple linear reduced-order model is derived. It approximates the fundamental work contributions and uses their superposition to generate stability maps from only 4 aeroelastic simulations instead of 40. This model enables rapid stability assessment without extensive computational resources.

Future work will focus on validating the assumptions made in this study and applying the methodology to different fan geometries.

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